

ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL, AND GOVERNANCE (“ESG”) PERFORMANCE AND FINANCIAL OUTCOMES: ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF “ESG” ON “FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE”

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ABSTRACT

Consideration of “Environmental, social, and governance (“ESG”)” has increased importance for the “financial performance” and financial market and it serves as a corporate manifestation of sector sustainable development, most corporate leaders accept the concern of “ESG” as a significant approach to enhance its ““financial performance””. The practices of “ESG” factors also contribute to a better dynamic of cost management, innovation and employee retention that further leads to a more sustainable prospect for long-term growth.

“ESG” performance has contributed towards the growth of “financial performance” through influencing investment decisions on “ESG” scoring firms among investors as well as contributing towards the inclination of firms to opt for social responsibility and environmental performance as well as corporate governance as a means for securing the support and investment participation of prospective investors and stakeholders. The study also implied sustainability funding and socially responsible investments and funding such as the ETF not only being limited towards investment contribution but also is included into the “financial performance” such as through investment and socially responsible funding assets and returns. Therefore, it could be considered that “ESG” performance has a positive and noteworthy influence over “financial performance” through a financial and non-financial parameters and integrations into businesses that shape the market value and “financial performance” of the forms due to the aspect of high “ESG” scoring firms having and upper hand in sustainability development within the firm and contribution towards sustainability in environment and society.

Keywords: Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG), Financial Performance Sustainability Development, Socially Responsible Investments, Corporate Governance

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INTRODUCTION

The “ESG” considerations” are progressively predominant towards investment choices on a global level. The criteria of “ESG” are principal collection that investors use to assess possible investments based on “operational activities”. Efforts of the company to battle climate change can minimise the emission of greenhouse gases, employ renewable energy and for manage waste. Examining the factor of “ESG” on “financial performance” includes assessing how the sustainability practices of a company are related to corporate governance, environmental impact and social responsibility may influence the overall valuation of the market, risk profile and profitability. It may often help in the lead to improve the financial result by using factors like accessibility to a wide base of investors, enhanced reputation and cost reduction. The performance of the “ESG” measures the way an organisation manages the opportunities and risks that are also associated with its factors. The investors can also implement “ESG” criteria to analyse possible investments based on the operations. The research focuses on exploring the influences of the “ESG” factor on “financial performance”.

RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVE

The present research aims on exploring the relationship and impact of “environmental social and governance (ESG) performance” on “financial performance”. The same is divided into the following objectives.

- To explore the influence of ESG performance on investment decisions as a factor of financial performance and outcomes.
- To evaluate the financial activities related to ESG having an impact on financial performance and outcomes
- To analyse ESG performance based investments and funding influencing financial activities and performance on a regional and global basis

RESEARCH QUESTION

The research had followed through investigating the following research questions.

- What influence does ESG performance have on investment decisions as a factor of financial performance and outcomes?
- What financial activities related to ESG have an impact on the financial performance and outcomes?
- How are ESG performance based investment and funding impacting the financial activities and performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ESG factors and financial performance

The “ESG” concept was proposed in the report published by the “United Nations Principles for Responsible Investment (UNPRI)” in 2002. UNPRI argues that the responsible investor thoroughly considers “ESG”’s impact on the value of the investment, as the view gained an increasing rate of prominence in global investment choice (Fu and Li, 2023). For investors, the criteria of “ESG” criteria become a collection of principles which can be used to evaluate potential investments based on the operational activities of the company. The performance of the “ESG” can boost the “financial performance”, which impacts industry regulation, business administrators, investors and decision-makers (Gao *et al.* 2022). Under the “Dual carbon goals”, the interest in connection between the “financial performance” and “ESG” is increasing among different sectors. Sustainable development perspective, the enterprise concentrates on the utilisation of rational resources and environmental protection provides long-term development factors and supports the more sustainable development of business. The frameworks of “ESG” are mainly used to assess the business practices of organisations and the performance of ethical and sustainability issues.

The financial instruction develops the internal criteria for “ESG” assessment and allocates the growing budget. The effect of the “ESG” factor on the “financial performance” becomes pronounced as if the market and customers are learning to rely on the indicators. Measurement of “ESG” is not helpful for easily generating the market-level confidence (Dragomir *et al.* 2022). However, there investors and customers understand the scoring and assessment of “ESG” so that these factors can have a visible influence on the financial factor of the finance sector. The modern literature work confirms the need for the risk management of “ESG”, proving that organisations with low risk of “ESG” are more attractive to the investor, and improve financial competitiveness and performance (Egorova *et al.* 2022). It also states that the trends towards socially responsible investment affect stock return predictability. Investor are also channels funds o with a better rating of “ESG” factor as these factors are impacting the value of the company. The companies use the dynamic of “ESG reporting in accounting” to evaluate the impact and assess the performance of the potential investments.

Figure 1: STOXX Europe ESG Leaders 50 ranking

(Source: Koundouri *et al.* 2022)

The relation of “ESG” performance could be observed through the aspect of sustainability and resilience. Studies such as Koundouri *et al.* (2022) imply the existence of an overall positive correlation among the aspects of “ESG metric performance” and “financial performance” of firms and organizations. As the study presented through the instance of the European market, “ESG” leader companies have a tendency of higher resilience in uncertain times. For instance, in the study, it was observed that the companies under EURO STOXX 50 companies had a sharper price fall by around 45% during the unprecedented time of COVID-19, while it was slightly lower in the case of firms identified under STOXX Europe “ESG” Leaders 50 companies, with price dropping by 42% (Koundori *et al.* 2022).

Policymaking and regulation on a global level have gained higher attention regarding integration of environmental, social, and governance responsibility. Studies have indicated that there is a relationship among either of the components of “ESG” performance such as through environmental performance, social performance and corporate performance. In the case of environmental performance in relation to “financial performance”, corporate environmental performance is considered as positively interrelated according to studies (Zhou *et al.* 2022). This could be considered through the relation between the environmental performance and “financial performance” by the factor of strengthening of environmental control causing improved operating efficiency and reduced environmental management costs improving “financial performance”. Although studies also suggest the relation between social and corporate governance performance with “financial performance” to not be as positively related, and have conditioned or negative correlations among each other.

Impacts of ESG practices and performance on corporate financial performance

“ESG” practices and its related performance has an impact on the development and execution of corporate “financial performance”. Studies suggest the integrating influence that environmental performance has on the existing corporate “financial performance” through the implication that environmental practice influences enhancement of “financial performance” (Saygili *et al.* 2022). The study also implies the presence of lower financial risks being tied to better corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities and performance as well as indicated studies presenting that low and high CSR are capable of increasing corporate “financial performance”, with the instance of companies having more social responsibility disclosure having higher market value. Furthermore, theoretical underpinnings such as the stakeholder theory have instigated the implication the “financial performance” and achievements of firms are related to the factor of relationships with not only the shareholders but also extending to the stakeholders of the firm’s operating environment (Shin *et al.* 2023). The influential relation is justified through the study through indicating the compliance of firms with the expectation of the stakeholders have a means for catering to the development of the performance through accumulation of support and appreciation of the firms.

“ESG” activities are also considered to have been impacting the firm value and “financial performance” of firms. These, according to studies, have identified the positive association among the relation of “ESG” activities and firm performance with the implication of CSR activities being capable of satisfying the expectation of stakeholders and contributing towards a higher corporate performance in the long term (Hwang *et al.* 2021). The studies also imply that there is a possibility for the fact that CSR activities have an effect through the environmentally and socially responsible activities alongside good corporate governance capable of meeting the demands and interests of stakeholders that are identified to be capable of contributing towards the improvement of “financial performance” of firms.

The study had indicated this to be the case due to the application of socially responsible activities and intangible assets, the intangible assets are capable of contributing to the positive development of “financial performance”. There are also studies that indicate the positive impact of “ESG” performance having an impact on the financial outcome such Indian companies companies with higher “ESG” performance having better “financial performance”, and companies in Germany showing “ESG” performance showing a positive relation with profitability of the companies (Naeem and Çankaya, 2022). Studies indicate an impactful relation of “ESG” on the development of “financial performance” and outcomes such as Institutional as well as individual investors take part in looking for attractive financial returns related to its positive influence on community and environment. The study also indicated a higher tendency of companies to be more attentive towards sharing “ESG” issues with the public for gaining the attention of investors. From a theoretical perspective through the implication of stakeholder theory the construction of Corporate “ESG” is capable of re-envisioning the aim of maximizing Corporate values through the integration of CSR considerations (Hu *et al.* 2023). The implementation of this would indicate through the transformative impact that “ESG” initiatives have on firms and organisations. Firms are enabled to accurately assess social capital as well as find the business cooperation networks that contribute towards the alleviation of resource constraints in production procedures.

As seen in the above studies it can be presumed that “ESG” performance having a positive impact on “financial performance” it can be seen that multiple national and regional industries in markets undergo the change of trends in relation with “ESG” application and use. Thereby it could be considered that the influence of “ESG” through CSR and other related activities has a significant and seemingly mostly positive impact on “financial performance” and its associated activities such as firm performance and market performance that contribute towards “financial performance” of the involved companies.

METHODOLOGY

The following research is a study that was intended to collect and investigate empirical information from existing research and data accessible regarding the subject. The following research had focused on collecting the information through the application of secondary data collection methods for the collection of qualitative and empirical data. The data hence collected includes information from published reports and research studies from accessible and available sources for information. The development of the following research is done in association to the research objectives and questions that intend to investigate “ESG” performance and “financial performance” in relation to the influences of the former on the latter.

The data collection had executed a purposive sampling for the accumulation of search based data collection procedure as a means for selection and integration of research information in relation to the study. The collected data was evaluated and further investigated in order to evaluate the impacts of “ESG” performance on “financial performance” through the empirical data. This is followed through by data analysis of the secondary empirical data related to this specific study subject. The results section displays the examined empirical data that had been gathered and evaluated hence using secondary data collection and analysis procedures under the focus of an exploratory research design.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact of “ESG” is considered in association with the influence that “environmental, social and governance factors” have on the performance of financial and firm level development. Investment and market value are considerably gaining the attention of becoming attached to the success or efficiency of “ESG” factors and their index rating among companies for investors. “ESG” has been having an impact on the private equity companies and their investors particularly in association with the influence of “ESG” performance only company “financial performance”. This could be associated with the factor of investments and environment of shareholder engagement being a result of private equity investment on private equity companies based on “ESG” practices development and disclosures (Bani-Harouni *et al.* 2023). Investors of private equity companies are capable of driving positive outcomes within their interested portfolio companies that are given the will to contribute to the benefit of both the sustainability as well as financial problems objectives of businesses.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (“ESG”) Performance and Financial Outcomes: Analyzing the Impact of “ESG” on “Financial Performance”

Figure 2: ESG performance impact on Europe private equity firms’ “financial performance”, 2023
(Source: Statista, 2024)

As seen through the above graphical evidence, “ESG” performance has an impact on private equity firms and their final performance with an example of the example of European companies. Around 53% of private equity companies have seen an improvement of brand perception of their own or portfolio companies as well as around 47% of private equity companies in Europe have observed and revenue potential increase from consumer demand and brand loyalty. Around 25% of private equity firms have observed and enhanced “financial performance” as a result of “operational efficiency” due to “ESG” benefits (Statista, 2024). Moreover almost 32% of companies in Europe operating as private equity funds have observed a long term financial benefit through supporting a just transition as well as 32% of the private equity companies in Europe have observed ad reduction of cost such as taxation and overhead.

“financial performance” is positively impacted by “ESG” performance through the implication that sustainable development activities are capable of attracting a higher demand for product and services among prospective consumers. A positive relationship between “financial performance” and “ESG” performance is considered to be associated with the growth and lower business risk being promoted through sustainable development (Junius *et al.* 2020). Market performance and market value of organisations are impacted through sustainability that is dependent on “ESG” performance. The positive implication of relationship between the two factors could also be considered through the aspect of increase in the cash flow that is gained by sustainable development activities taken part in by the company through the practice of CSR and generation report causing an increase in market value among prospective investors and consumers.

Figure 3: ESG drivers impacting investment decisions by region, 2023

(Source: Statista, 2024)

“ESG” has an impact on the development of sustainability of companies as well as the integrated activities businesses consider in executives that further on attracts the attention of investors that are socially and environmentally conscious in terms of making investment decisions. There are several components considered to be driving “ESG” impact towards investment decision making that is applicable for several regions. “ESG” ratings are one of the most necessary factors that influence investment decision or a global level which around 71% of investors implied being influential in the decision making with around 27% of these institutional investors being from Europe around 17% of them from the US around 2% of them from Asia Pacific and around 25% of them from Canada (Statista, 2024). Easy controversy is considered as the second largest factor with around 60% of investors considered in it to be an influential component impacting the investment decisions. While 52% of investors regard GHG emissions as a considerable influence towards investment decision making.

Social responsible companies are capable of attracting the attention of investors through their outlook of being sustainable and contributing towards long term sustainability development and positive changes for the environment and society alongside their policies and governance practices aligning with their goal. Non-financial parameters are considered for the implementations of such policies that have become more essential for investors to consider before making investment decisions in an evolved attempt from the conventional practice of considering financial profits as a major factor for investment decision making (Aich *et al.* 2021).

Environmental, Social, and Governance (“ESG”) Performance and Financial Outcomes: Analyzing the Impact of “ESG” on “Financial Performance”

“ESG” investing is becoming an influential component that has included nonfinite shell parameters for the use of investors to apply as a major for analysing the profit and growth opportunities of the companies they might invest in. This makes “ESG” investing as a financial activity that is driven by the influence of “ESG” performance upon “financial performance” and outcome related to financial activities partaken among the companies and their stakeholders as an investment factor and factor for evaluation of profit and financial growth.

Figure 4: Global ESG ETF assets, 2003-2023

(Source: Statista, 2024)

“ESG” criteria as a set of principles implemented by investors for the analysis of company performance in consideration with prospective investments. Around 480 billion US dollars have been invested as value of effect to ETF funds including “ESG” goals within strategies in the year 2023 in comparison to 391 billion US dollars in 2021 (Statista, 2024). As of recently making investments into sustainable funds also include ETF funds that are considered to be primarily driven by the developed market particularly in the US and Europe. The “ESG” criteria set for investors to evaluate company performance regarding making investment decisions includes evaluation of the environmental perspective of protecting the environment. In terms of social point of view, it is seen that investors considered the impacts of business upon the local community as well as stakeholder relations.

The component of governance in case of “ESG” investing is evaluated with an easy perspective of internal controls, stakeholder rights and executive pays.

Implications of findings indicate that “ESG” funding of “ESG” ETF funds are impacted by the influence of these applications to financial development. The relationship between sustainability and fund Returns chut the application of sustainability ratings imply a relationship between sustainability and financial returns to be rather low in nature. Moreover the factor of risk adjusted returns of funds alongside higher sustainability scores are capable of corresponding towards the returns of the funds without high scores (Rompotis, 2023). However it needs to be considered that socially responsible investors are capable of personal social or sustainability regards without the prospective loss in “financial performance” terms as well as releasing financial benefits. This can be considered with the fact that studies indicate almost no significant difference in financial returns for companies with either high or low “ESG” ratings.

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“ESG” performance and ratings regarding financial activities have an impact on not only the “financial performance” but also the related firm value development and market value development aspect. Studies have indicated the implication of PSG scores and see “financial performance” of organisations to have a potentially negative relationship as well as utilising sudden factors such as firms with a low social scope having a better performance then the market (Aydoğmuş *et al.* 2022). The implication of financial return of “ESG” performance indicates that high “ESG” performance in ETFs is not capable of ensuring protection during a severe decline of the market.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (“ESG”) Performance and Financial Outcomes: Analyzing the Impact of “ESG” on “Financial Performance”

Figure 5: S&P 500 ESG and S&P 500 indexes performance differences, 2021-2024

(Source: Statista, 2024)

“ESG” factors are considered as an influential element towards the “financial performance” and activities of the company involved in the evaluation of the prospective growth and resilience with the consideration of sustainability within the company that is often examined through the evaluation of “ESG” and index for market capitalization. For instance the performance among the S&P 500 “ESG” index companies and S&P 500 index, was evaluated and observed that the performance is particularly within the similar industries. On February 22, 2021, the S&P 500 “ESG” and S&P 500 index both comparisons showed that around 22nd February 2021 the scores were 99.22 and 99.23 respectively (Statista, 2024). In 2022 the scores had increased to 114.02 and 110.19 respectively. It is also to be noted that around the year 2023 the values 105.14 and 102.16 were the index value of S&P “ESG” 500 companies and S&P index companies were again also indicating a similar range of performance.

The implication of “ESG” scores and index course for market capitalisation are ranging within the similar range of values indicating the influence of “ESG” being capable of integrating resilience organisations. CSR and “ESG” related disclosures have an impact on the “financial performance” of organisations and certain studies also indicate a significant negative relationship among the two.

This could be due to the fact that socially responsible practices are prone to suffering from more financial cost and having a lower operation and “financial performance”. However, certain components of measurement such as the evaluation of US S&P 500 market performance includes the relationship between “CSR disclosure” and “market performance” to have a positive relationship (Alareeni and Hamdan, 2020). This indicates that S&P 500 companies are potentially sharing and awareness and consideration towards CSR practices being main driving forces for market performances as well as contributing towards the significance and usefulness of market value development. Further or it is recognised the tendency of hired “ESG” in firms and companies with high assets and financial leverage. This could imply PSG to be an influential factor of higher market performance and “financial performance” capacities.

Figure 6: Socially responsible investments (SRI) and “financial performance” in Italy, 2017

(Source: Statista, 2022)

Socially responsible investments and its relevance of contributing towards the development of “financial performance” and influence by SG criteria is considered as one of the influential factors of financial activities such as investment behaviour. With the example of Italy it can be seen that around 45% of investors recognise socially responsible investments being quite relevant to the aspect of investment decision making in terms of “financial performance” of a company being relevant (Statista, 2022). Socially responsible investments and funding contribute towards the development of financial activities and investment attitude of investors into prospective portfolio companies.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (“ESG”) Performance and Financial Outcomes: Analyzing the Impact of “ESG” on “Financial Performance”

The ESG factor and criteria is a considerable element that is capable of influencing the decisions of investors as well as meeting with potential expectations of “ESG” criteria yielding potential excess returns. This is due to the fact that a company with a high “ESG” criteria score is capable of combating or managing environmental and social crises further on contributing towards cost reduction and in turn an improved “financial performance” (Hornuf and Yüksel, 2024). An increased demand of investors having “ESG” preferences is capable of driving companies to shift towards socially responsible investment in recent years with high assets scoring on “ESG” criteria having presented positive returns.

Figure 7: Share investors increasing ESG ETF in the US, Europe and China, 2024

(Source: Statista, 2024)

“ESG” ETF investments and allocation heavily gained a momentous increase with the passing recent years due to its implication on investments on environmental social and governance factors. Around 74% of the investors in the US, Europe and China, as of 2024, have indicated wanting to increase investments on “ESG” within the next year (Statista, 2024). Studies indicate the environment of “ESG” risk factors and scores being impactful on Exchange- Traded Funds performance particularly in association with risk adjusted performance. The implication of ESG risk impacting risk adjusted performance of the ETF is due to the fact that environmental risks are specifically critical in terms of maintaining a favourable risk adjusted return of the ETF (Landi *et al.* 2024).

Impacts of “environmental” as well as “social” and “governance” risk in association with the fact of environmental sustainability being important towards investment performance that also contribute potentially towards financial benefits and hence force “financial performance” being somewhat influenced by “ESG” risk.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion to the above research, it can be perceived that “ESG” performance has a complex means of influencing “financial performance” through several components that include market, corporate financial activities as well as market and firm value and performance. The study indicated the influence of “ESG” as a factor of influencing investor attitude as well as contributing towards funding and investment decision making for firm through innovating the investor decision making criteria by including non-financial parameters into conventional perspective of profitability as investment criteria. “ESG” performance such as “ESG” risk scores and “ESG” metric score regarding environmental social and governance performance among organizations having an influence on “financial performance” and activities such as funding and investments as well as financial returns and benefits alongside financial profitability and development of corporate “financial performance” and market value of firms. Sustainability funding and socially responsible investment such as ETF had also been recognised as financial activities involved with investment and “financial performance” development instigators for PSG supported sustainability development within firms and instilling firm contribution towards sustainability development in environment and society alongside positive “financial performance”.

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Environmental, Social, and Governance (“ESG”) Performance and Financial Outcomes:
Analyzing the Impact of “ESG” on “Financial Performance”

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